

male sterile (CMS) lines. Two indices were used: (1) pollen morphology and staining pattern and (2) type of interaction with a set of maintainers and restorers of wild abortive (WA) cyto sterile stock. The newly developed CMS lines are grouped using these indices as follows: I. RPMS1 (*O. rufipogon*; VNI) and RPMS2 (*O. nivara*; DRW21039) are gametophytic types; II. RPMS3 (*O. nivara*; DRW21030) is similar to MS577A in pollen stainability, but the restoration and maintenance reactions are similar to those of

the WA type; III. RPMS4 (*O. nivara*; DRW21018) is a sporophytic type, but restorers and maintainers are different from WA; IV. RPMS5 and RPMS6 (*O. nivara*; RPW21111) are sporophytic types with restorer and maintainer reactions similar to those of WA. All the new CMS lines possessed complete panicle exertion essential for enhancing outcrossed seed yield.

For the two stable CMS lines, MS577A and IR66707A, no restorers are available in cultivated rice germplasm. A search for restorer sources for these

CMS lines was made among the wild accessions of the A genome species. Although none of the accessions could restore fertility in IR66707A, three accessions of *O. rufipogon* (VN2, DRW22016, DRW220175) and one each from *O. sativa* f. *spontanea* (RPW20001) and *O. glaberrima* (DRGL 30090) did restore fertility in MS577A. Studies on the genetics of fertility restoration in these cross combinations indicated that two dominant genes act in an additive manner to restore fertility. ■

Krishna CMS lines in the background of four different cytoplasmic sources in rice

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Four cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines of Krishna with sterile cytoplasm from four different sources (wild abortive [WA], *O. perennis*, Kalinga 1, and Lalruma from Mizoram) have been developed. The two CMS lines—Krishna A with WA and Krishna A with *O. perennis* as a source—were developed through conversion with CMS lines V20A (WA) and IR66707A (*O. perennis*), respectively, by subsequent backcrossing with common isonuclear main-

tainer Krishna A. But Krishna A with Kalinga 1 and Krishna A with Lalruma cytoplasmic sources were developed through indica / indica crosses. These four CMS lines are all dwarf in stature, are of medium duration, and have reduced white anthers that exhibit 80-90% unstained withered pollen grains.

To understand the nature of these four cyto sterility sources, they were testcrossed with four maintainers—V20B (maintainer of WA), IR66707B (maintainer of *O. perennis*), Yar-Ai-ZhaoB (maintainer of Gambiaca), and MS577B (maintainer of *O. sativa* f. *spontanea*)—and the elite inbred lines SPR7210-1-3, IR48725-B-B-120-1, NDR30074, TTB150-61, and R657-93-869. The sterility of the four CMS lines was maintained by the four main-

tainers. The restorer SPR7210-1-3 of Krishna A (WA) was found to be a maintainer of the other three CMS lines—Krishna A (*O. perennis*), Krishna A (Kalinga 1), and Krishna A (Lalruma)—whereas the restorer IR48725-B-B-120-1 of Krishna A (WA) behaved as partial restorer of Krishna A (Kalinga 1) and Krishna A (Lalruma) and as a maintainer of Krishna A (*O. perennis*). Variety R657-93-869 was found to be a partial restorer of Krishna A (WA) and Krishna A (Lalruma) and a maintainer of Krishna A (Kalinga 1) and Krishna A (*O. perennis*). The restorer TTB150-61 for Krishna A (Lalruma) behaved as a partial restorer of Krishna A (WA) and Krishna A (Kalinga 1), and as a maintainer of Krishna A (*O. perennis*). ■

Characterizing thermo-sensitive genic male sterile lines of rice

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The cytoplasmic male sterility (CMS) system is widely used to develop rice hybrids. Although effective, this system is quite cumbersome to practice. Certain genic male sterile lines that revert to fertility under specific temperature are called thermosensitive genic male sterile (TGMS) lines. Deployment of the TGMS system to develop two-line hybrids has several

advantages over the conventional CMS system, as it requires neither maintainers for seed multiplication nor restorers for producing hybrids. In addition, two-line hybrids may not suffer from possible negative effects of the sterility-inducing cytoplasm. For an effective use of TGMS lines, they have to be characterized for their critical sterility and fertility points. This information is essential for deciding on a suitable location and / or period for seed multiplication and hybrid seed production. Two IRRI-bred indica TGMS lines-IR68945-4-33-4-14 and IR68949-11-5-31-along with their japonica TGMS donor, were charac-

terized under controlled conditions in the IRRI phytotron. These lines were subjected to eight constant temperatures (20-32 °C) and four day-night combination temperatures (27 / 21 °C-32 / 24 °C) for a period of 3 wk during the sensitive stage. The critical sterility point for both lines was 30 °C and above, whereas it was only 27 °C and above for Norin PL 12. The critical fertility points for the indica TGMS lines ranged between 24-28 °C (constant temperate) and 27 / 21 °C-28 / 22 °C (day-night combination temperature). Norin PL 12 was found to be very sensitive to higher temperature compared with the indica TGMS lines.